

CS TRACK
Investigating Citizen Science

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First publication of the e-magazine D5.2

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Executive summary	This deliverable explains and documents the process followed from the preparation of Deliverable 5.1 to the launch of the e-Magazine and the publication of the first issue. First, an overview of the general aspects of the e-Magazine is made from the previous description developed. The most relevant technical issues are detailed as well as the structure of the e-Magazine and the type of content that will be incorporated into the e-Magazine from this first edition is specified. Next, the editorial process that has been approved by the consortium for the publication of the contents in the e-Magazine is described. The different agents that participate in the process are indicated (authors, multimedia editors, external collaborators, team leader and editorial committee), and it is explained how the editorial workflow works both when contributions are made by researchers who are part of the consortium partners and when an external specialist is invited. This section concludes with the explanation of the production process that is carried out for the elaboration of the articles. The next block develops the e-Magazine scheduling and the details of this first publication. Finally, the references used for the Editorial Guidelines are indicated, which are followed by both the authors, the multimedia editor, and the Editorial Committee in order to guarantee the highest quality of the publications.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable describes the process that has been followed to do the first publication of the e-Magazine. It also refers to the way the dashboard has been integrated and put in operation within the e-Magazine.

This deliverable relates directly to the description of technical requirements and the plan for the implementation of the Community Platform described in the Deliverable D5.1. Its development has considered the technical and final users' needs as well as the requirements to simplify as much as possible the work to do by the consortium partners.

Likewise, it becomes necessary to consider the milestones carried out so far because they describe the evolution and the achievements associated with the launch of the Community platform.

Milestone 5.1 Launch of the Community Platform Site 1 (M5.1)

- Date. 30 September
- Explanation/Description. The development of the community platform required some adjustments to incorporate additional functions. They were carried out in the first days in September 2020. To this effect, we had worked hard on it in the test web and some test had been implemented with the consortium partners to verify it. The launch took place on September 30th, presenting the community platform. Until now, it explained the contents it will include and made a call to action to attract the users' attention, inviting them to subscribe to CS Track newsletter (see Figure 1)
- What was done? As indicated in D5.1, M5.1 draws on analysis data elaborated from different WPs, since the community platform is structured around published analytical information. As analytical results have become available, it has been possible to start configuring the platform, which has generated a slight delay to meet the requirement established in M5.1. In September the platform was being tested with partners in the development environment, and the first version was published. In this first version, the main characteristics are shown and a call to action is made so that the target audiences know about it and can subscribe to the newsletter, opening this communication channel.

Figure 1. Notice of coming soon from the e-Magazine on the CS-Track website

Milestone 5.2. Launch of the Community Platform Site 2 with e-Magazine and multiple languages (M5.2)

- Date. 30 November
- Explanation/Description. As noted in D5.1, we have worked on improving of the workflow about editorial policy and establishing the e-Magazine Community Platform to offer relevant information of an analytical nature about the platforms, projects and initiatives of Citizen Science. It will comprise also recommendations, reports and other resources that highlight the value of Citizen Science and the way it can be supported to improve its results and make strategic decisions to boost its development. These improvements have been incorporated into the development of the community platform in this version 2. In this process, it was decided to focus the efforts on strengthening the content published in the lingua franca of the CS Track project (English) with the aim of obtaining the greatest possible reach to its target audiences.
- What was done? The e-Magazine Community Platform includes different ways of accessing information through a single communication channel. It provides three different formats where users can get information from graphic articles, reports and a newsletter. At the same time, the e-Magazine Community Platform allows connecting and involving different actors (policymakers, academics and practitioners, among others) interested in the analysis of Citizen Science. For this reason, it is planned to include one explicit reference of the intended audience in every article. This aspect will be related to the target defined in the CS Track project, so that, once the e-Magazine has reached a large enough volume of articles it will permit carrying out an easier filtering by the target audiences. Finally, with respect to the community

platform language, we are considering the installation of a complement or a plug-in to add this specific function.

Regarding its structure, this Deliverable D5.2 covers the following aspects:

- An overview of the e-Magazine with different analytic perspectives: technical, structural and about the content.
- Devising an editorial process and defining the several agents involved in it.
- Establish the workflow to achieve, by the end of the project, the publications determined in D5.1.
- And, finally, a brief description of the editorial guidelines on style and some recommendations about gender and ethical aspects that will be implemented and reflected in our actions as multimedia editors.

2. Overview of e-Magazine

2.1. Technical description

As described in Deliverable D5.1, the e-Magazine is an electronic magazine that includes articles prepared by the project's experts. It takes up and communicates interesting findings gathered through our analytics and empirical studies. Also, the readers can find and explore specific information based on the data collected during the research through built-in control panels as a specific type of post.

However, the final version of the e-Magazine that is presented here is the result of several improvements which have been incorporated after various stages and includes several types of contents. In this regard, the next paragraph elaborates on the evolution of the different communication channels described in D5.1 to create a community platform.

Evolution and versions of the e-Magazine

The first idea was to develop the e-Magazine like a social network wall with different areas (private and public) and sections (see Annex 1). This idea was rejected because it did not serve well as a Community Platform proposal.

Later, we worked on how to create a "Community of practice that facilitated a bidirectional channel to allow community members to share the questions that interest them in Citizen Science". To this end, the community of practice might have been composed of the following elements: website, newsletter and the e-Magazine (CS Community).

In respect to this, the **first version** of the **website** might have contained information regarding the CS Track project and give access to the rest of the communication channels mentioned previously.

In line with this, the **first version of the e-Magazine** was designed to create content to reach the communities connected with the consortium. Thus, the e-Magazine as a CS community should provide articles regarding the CS Track Project and be a space to share scientific and policy knowledge to facilitate dialogue between different stakeholders. Regarding its function, it should offer relevant information about the project results and key outcomes, as well as recommendations, and supply an interactive space to exchange knowledge about Citizen Science.

The community platform, through the e-Magazine, should communicate and share the project's findings on issues such as:

- Understand the participation patterns
- Learn about incentives, disincentives, barriers, and enablers
- Learn about scientific, societal, economic, and democratic benefits

In the following image we can see how the first version of the e-Magazine, within the website, was planned:

Figure 2. Initial planning of menu items on the web

In relation to the **first version of the newsletter** it would be necessary a subscription to receive the content. Also, it should be necessary providing information about:

- News and events from CS track project.
- Content published in e-Magazine (reports and technical products and citizen science)
- Curated information that will not be suitable to be published in News and events section (published on Twitter).

The summary of the second version of the website is shown in the following image:

- 1) The website should provide general information about the project and give access to the Community platform, the e-Magazine and the Newsletter subscription.
- 2) The Community platform should be a space where all target groups can interact.
- 3) The e-Magazine should be composed of the articles with content related to the results of the CS Track project.
- 4) The newsletter should summarize the content of website, and specifically the section of news, e-Magazine articles and other curated content that is not suitable for being published in any of the other communication channels. It should also be pointed out that, later, an overview (a brief paragraph) about communication actions from CS Track project was added. In the following images it is shown the different contents that subscribers will receive in their emails.

Newsletter

Figure 3. Contents of Newsletter

As well, in this second version we more concretely specified the Community Platform as a **dashboard**, that is, a panel that provide graphic information synthetically to allow the CS community to improve its knowledge on Citizen Science.

Finally, a new notion was proposed regarding the dashboard, making it accessible from the e-Magazine through some selected data associated with different types of content. In the following image we can see the final version of the e-Magazine within CS Track website before the first publication.

Figure 6. Final version e-Magazine before the first publication

In this regard, it should be noticed that the appearance of the e-Magazine will depend on the different (and changing) contents that will be shown on it, such as graphical articles or reports as shown the next image.

Figure 7. Layout depending on the type of article published

Classification

All articles include information indicating the main group of users of the CS-Track Community to which the content is directed. For each article, the target audience is identified. It is indicated which are the main audience and which are the secondary ones, attending to those identified in Deliverable 5.1.

By means of an active tagging system (tags and categories), readers can find out the target audience as well as navigate directly to other articles categorized for said audiences.

Audience: **Academics** | **Heads of organizations** | **Practitioners**

Categories: **Reports**

Metadata

In the final stage of the technical development, we paid special attention to maximizing the findability and recoverability of the contents published in the e-Magazine to ensure that the community of interest in Citizen Science can locate these quickly, whether they know the CS-Track project and want to reach the material from the project's channels or they located those contents through external search.

To improve SEO (Search Engine Optimization) a plugin has been incorporated to facilitate the management of both the e-Magazine globally and each of the published articles.

At a general level, the settings for titles and meta tags, taxonomies, files, etc., have been optimized; the XML sitemap, the image sitemap and the HTML sitemap of the site have been created. Analytics tracking system using Google Analytics has also been included to evaluate the use made by readers and incorporate evolutionary improvements.

Figure 8. Metadata manager

This plugin allows also including metadata under this Dublin Core (DC) standard as well as under the Open Graph Metadata (OG) standard in each published post.

Figure 9. Metadata manager settings

```

<meta name="DC.Publisher" content="CS Track" />
<meta name="DC.Language" scheme="UTF-8" content="en-GB" />
<meta name="DC.Creator" content="CS Track" />
<meta name="DC.Description" content="&nbsp; [rt_reading_time label=Reading Time: postfix=minutes p
<meta name="DC.Type" scheme="DCMIType" content="Text" />
<meta name="DC.Format" scheme="IMT" content="text/html" />
<meta name="DC.Format.MIME" content="text/html" />
<meta name="DC.Format.SysReq" content="Internet browser" />
<meta name="DC.Source" content="https://cstrack.eu/">
<meta name="DC.Coverage" content="World">
<meta name="DC.Identifier" content="https://cstrack.eu/reports/evolution-academic-publications-cit:
<meta name="DC.Date" content="2020-12-31" />
<meta name="DC.Subject" content="Reports" />
<meta content="Ciberimaginario Divi Child Theme v.1.0" name="generator"/><style type="text/css">
img.wp-smilev.

```

Figure 10. Code with metadata in Dublin Core format

With respect to each article, the title, meta description and target keywords are optimized to obtain the best snippets. In addition, a content analysis is carried out that includes social meta tags, keyword density, compliance with content accessibility requirements (alternative texts ...), headings, structured data, etc.

Figure 11. Article-level metadata editor

2.2. Structure and content description

The structure of the articles it fits to the following mockup:

Figure 12. Mock-up of a standard article

The e-Magazine publications may correspond to two different types of content:

- **Graphical article.** It is a panel that provides graphic information synthetically and will show the data stored in the database of CS Track project to the users. In this case, the comment system is not activated. An example is shown in the following image:

Does citizen science have a presence in academic publications?

by CS Track Admin | Sep 29, 2020 | Dashboard Item

Since 2004, academic publications on citizen science are growing significantly every year

More than 70% of the publications are journal articles

Although citizen science was defined in the mid/1990s by Rick Bonney in the United States (Bonney, 1996) and Alan Irwin in the United Kingdom (Irwin, 1995) it is not until 2005 that the number of academic publications in this area begins to grow (Figure 1). More than 70% of the publications have been published in journals, while more than 17% of those are conference papers.

How to interpretate this data

The first visualization is a line bar showing the number of publications related to citizen science in Scopus per year. The second visualization is a pie chart that shows the number of publications per type of publication.

Legend

The legend is included in the different charts.

Figure 13. Graphical article example

- Report.** This refers to articles with analyses carried out in the CS Track project. In addition, this content includes a comment system to ask any questions about the topic. An example is shown in the next image.

Evolution of academic publications in citizen science

BY DAVID ROLDÁN ÁLVAREZ | DEC 5, 2020 | REPORTS

Reading Time: 5 minutes

Citizen science is an area in which interest has increased over the years. People who are not professional scientists get involved in citizen science projects with the intention of solving a question that they find to be of interest. Traditionally, scientific discoveries are accompanied by academic publications that demonstrate the results obtained. However, the non-academic nature of citizen science means that such academic publications are not an intrinsic aspect of citizen science projects. In this post, we show how citizen science publication has evolved over the last 20 years.

Evolution of academic publications

Citizen science is the practice of using a large number of volunteers, rather than professional researchers, to collect data for scientific research. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavours that generate new knowledge or understanding. However, managing a large number of scientists is not a trivial task and in many instances the data provided has limitations and controls for bias need to be introduced. It is well known that the quality of data significantly affects publications in the academic field. Therefore, in this post we show how publications related to citizen science have evolved by using *Scopus*, an expertly curated abstract and citation database. We are working with a total of 19,182 publications dating from 1990 to 2019. Although citizen science was defined in the mid/1990s by Rick Bonney in the United States (Bonney, 1996) and Alan Irwin in the United Kingdom (Irwin, 1995) it was not until 2005 that the number of academic publications in this area began to grow.

Citizen science publications per year

Citations per year

Figure 14. Report article example

As a matter of terminology, note that in D5.1 this kind of content referred to e-Magazine articles and dashboard items, instead of reports or graphical articles, respectively, as presently called.

- **External collaboration.** In addition, there will be a possibility to invite external experts to contribute with specific articles for publication. The aim of this collaboration is to bring complementary points of view on the findings of the CS-Track project. This will enrich the e-Magazine's potential as a means to share knowledge about the Citizen Science.

2.3. Participation of the CS Community

The participation of the citizen science community in the Community Platform is a fundamental objective of the CS-Track project. To encourage this participation in the Community Platform the e-Magazine features a powerful comment system. The system allows several functions such as adding inline commenting and feedback; commenting on post content; live notification with real-time updating; making social commenting and rating posts directly on rating stars; etc.

This commenting system will be used for the reports, using a comment plugin for WordPress named *wpDiscuz*. Thus, if a public reader is interested in a piece of information or needs to go into detail about the report, he/she can ask a question, which will be passed to and answered by the author.

The steps for using this comment system are the following:

1. Someone asks a question in the report, getting to pend for approval by the administrator of the website.
2. The administrator of the website receives an email asking for his/her approval of the comment.
3. Once the comment is approved to appear in the report, the person who asked the question receives a mail to subscribe for new comments on our website. He/she can confirm his/her subscription or cancel it.

The following images detail the information necessary to make a comment in the report. It is necessary to fill name, email and check the reCAPTCHA.

The image shows a user interface for a feedback form. At the top left, there is a 'Subscribe' button with a dropdown arrow. At the top right, there is a 'Connect with' button. Below these is a large text area for the comment, starting with the prompt 'Be the First to Comment!'. The text area has a rich text editor toolbar with icons for bold (B), italic (I), underline (U), strikethrough (ABC), bulleted list, numbered list, quote, code, link, unlink, and a plus sign for more options. Below the text area are three input fields: 'Name*', 'Email*', and 'Website'. To the right of these fields is a reCAPTCHA widget with the text 'I'm not a robot' and a small robot icon. Below the reCAPTCHA is a 'Post Comment' button with a bell icon. At the bottom left, it says '0 COMMENTS'. At the bottom right, there are three small icons: a lightning bolt, a fire, and a heart.

Figure 15. Feedback form

In addition, it is possible to make a rating of the report. The readers can vote and give a rating to the article by stars, as shown below:

Figure 16. Article Rating

The following image explains in more detail the options for including comments.

Figure 17. Explanation of the comment system

3. Editorial Process

The editorial process comprises all the steps from the moment an author sends the content to the editors until it is published. The process is the same independently of the type of content involved.

Following the delivery of Deliverable 5.1 we have been working on improving the process to carry out the review by the editorial committee, editors, and authors. It is described in detail below.

3.1. Agents' Roles in the Editorial Process

Author

- The author is the researcher who writes the article and the person in charge of the content included in the article.
- Once it is finished, the author should send his/her proposal to a colleague/s from the same WP to review it. It will be the first review of the article, concentrating on content aspects (see the e-Magazine publication checklist).
- When the internal review is completed, the author will send the article to the multimedia editor.
- The author should be in touch with his/her colleague/s, the multimedia editor, and the editorial committee.

Multimedia editor

- The URJC team performs the work of the multimedia editor.
- The multimedia editor will be responsible to review the content on the second step, both in content and formal aspects (see the e-Magazine publication checklist).
- They will adapt the content as needed, create the media and publish a draft of the post. This draft is shared with all people involved in the review process: editorial committee, author/s and multimedia editor.
- To the extent needed, the multimedia editor will be in contact with the author and the editorial committee.

External Collaborator

- Researchers and external experts to CS Track project that have been invited to collaborate in the e-Magazine.
- Any member of the CS Track project may propose to the Editorial Committee an external collaborator. The Editorial Committee must approve this proposition before continuing with the process.
- Upon approval, the external collaborator becomes an author, taking part in the review process in a comparable manner to that of authors that are members of the project. His/her contribution will be supervised by the member who invited him/her to contribute.
- Leader/colleague
- A person (leader or colleague) who belongs to the same WP as the author's.
- His/her function consists in doing the first review of the article about the content aspects following the indications showed in the e-Magazine's checklist for publications.

- This person is expectedly very knowledgeable of the topic and he/she is aware of these because both he/she and his/her partners belong and work in the same WP.
- He/she and the author should be in touch with each other.

The following scheme summarizes the different agents and their functions in the internal editorial process.

Figure 18. Outline of the editorial process for publications by project authors

This other scheme details the different agents and their functions in the external editorial process.

Figure 19. Editorial process outline for guest author publications

Editorial Committee

The Editorial Committee is the body approved by the consortium to carry out the prior editorial review of the contents that are published in the e-Magazine. It has been set prior to the first publication of the e-Magazine.

The Editorial Committee is formed by voluntary members of the CS Track project. Their function is providing feedback to the article on several aspects such as content, technical or the quality of the English writing. The Committee reviews and suggests the appropriate modifications to the article in process.

Their functions change according to the type of content to be published:

- For internal researchers' publications: The Editorial Committee reviews for a second time the articles – both content and formal aspects – in cooperation with multimedia editor. Once the necessary changes recommended by the Editorial Committee are made, the following step is the language revision.
- For external researchers' publications, the Editorial Committee is accountable for approving the proposition for external input. Once approved, the Editorial Committee will follow the same guidelines explained above for internal researcher's publications.

In addition, to carry out this editorial process, an evaluation system (Editorial Committee publications checklist) has been elaborated. This includes the following steps:

Step 1

The author writes the article and sends it for a content review to one of his/her colleague/s from the same WP. The following evaluation emphases should be considered:

	Text	Title/Subtitle	Figures/Tables	Raw Data
Content aspects	The text includes the relevant aspects for its development.	The title is clear, and it replies to the content. The subtitles support to structure the document and guide the reader	Figures and tables provide all information needed to understand the report. If applies	Raw data presented are enough to carry out the charts or infographics. If applies

Step 2

Once this first revision has been done, the author/s send to the multimedia editor the article to adapt and create the multimedia content. In this respect, the multimedia editor creates and shares the document with the Editorial Committee to make the necessary changes. Now focus should be made on the following aspects (formal and content).

	Structure	Coherence	Result	Conclusion
Formal Aspects	The article contains all the aspects included in the Work Card.	The text is coherent. There is relation between all the concepts presented in the text and the presented	The results are detailed in the text and based on the data or the information provided.	The conclusions are detailed in the text and based on the results or the information provided.

		concepts are in line with CS Track's use of concepts.		(If applicable)
Content aspects	Text	Title/Subtitle	Figures/Tables	Raw Data
	The text includes the relevant aspects for its development.	The title is clear and suits the content. The subtitles support to structure the document and guide the reader	Figures and tables provide all information needed to understand the report. (If applicable)	Raw data presented are enough to carry out the charts or infographics. (If applicable)

Step 3

When the editorial committee has finished the review of the article and has made the observations for possible improvements, if needed the multimedia editor will contact the author to discuss the changes the editorial committee had suggested. This way, all those involved in the process will be informed about the different changes.

Step 4

The last review about the article is done for the Editorial Committee who carries out the language revision before launching the article in the e-Magazine. The article needs a positive valuation from the editorial committee to be published.

Observations for possible improvements		Is it publishable?	Yes / No
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3.2. Editorial workflow

Having defined the different editorial roles in the previous section, here we explain *the process* that an article undergoes since it is written until it is published, that is, the editorial workflow. In this respect, two different workflows were designed, one to publish the post of an internal member and the other to external collaborations.

Internal workflow

The following image shows the scheme of the first internal version of the editorial workflow.

Figure 20. First internal workflow version

The steps to follow in this first version of the workflow, before the publication of the first article, were as follows:

- The author wrote the article using the Work Card and sent it editing.
- The multimedia editor team made some adjustments to adapt the content, create the multimedia resources and published a draft to share.
- This draft was sent to the author to review it.
- Once the draft was corrected it was sent to the Editorial Committee to review again to validate it. The review of the different contents (graphical articles and reports) is done from several perspectives (technical, of content and linguistic aspects) to validate that the articles comply adequately with all the editorial requirements of quality to be published.

The above version of the workflow was eventually revised, as a result of technical meetings that were held with the editorial committee. It was decided to introduce some changes to improve the process.

The following image shows current version of the overall workflow of the editorial process. describes the various steps since a researcher writes on a topic until it is published in the e-Magazine.

Editorial Publication Workflow for Internal Researchers

Figure 21. Final version of the internal workflow

External workflow

The possibility of including external collaboration in the e-Magazine called for devising an appropriate version of the workflow to address this type of content in the editorial process.

Every team member in CS Track is welcome to suggest an external collaborator to write a report for publication in the project's e-Magazine. Since the number of publications is limited by the project's work plan, an external collaboration will be counted as an own (internal) one by the proposing partner, i.e., once the external report is published, the publication milestone will be considered as accomplished. However, the person who proposes the external collaboration will need to be responsible for this output, meaning that they will need to take an active part in the publication workflow by reviewing and making sure that the proposed article suits the requirements, and the editorial process is completed correctly.

The editorial process for an external collaboration is as follows:

1. Step 1. Contact the external collaborator
 - 1.1 Ask the potential collaborator to complete a 250-word paragraph explaining the main points of the content proposed for publication.
2. Step 2. Asking the Editorial Committee
 - 2.1 Once you have the paragraph above, send it to WP5 leaders to gather the Editorial Committee to decide.
3. Step 3. Getting the approval
 - 3.1 Within 1 week you will receive the answer. If the proposal is accepted follow the step 4. Otherwise, the Editorial Committee will contact the external expert to indicate the reason for the rejection.
4. Step 4. Asking the author to fill in the Work Card
 - 4.1 The procedure for creating the external collaboration output will be the same as for the internal process. Thus, you will need to ask the external collaborator to fill in the Report Work Card.
5. Step 5. Content Reviewing
 - 5.1 Once you receive the Work Card a content reviewing must be done by you and by colleagues from your WP (or others). The person who proposed the external collaboration will oversee the process, asking for this first review.
6. Step 6. Send the Work Card to WP5
 - 6.1 Once you send it to WP5, URJC team will follow the steps of the "Editorial Committee Publication Workflow for External Collaboration" (please check them). The Editorial Committee will make improvement suggestions and WP5 will contact you again before publishing the output.

The following infographic shows the editorial process to follow in cases of external proposals for publication in the e-Magazine.

Editorial Publication Workflow for External Collaboration

Figure 22. Final version of the external workflow

3.3. Content Production

As written before, the content production process involves many actors: researchers (internal and external), multimedia content creators and editors, and the Editorial Committee.

Two key instruments have been created to expedite the workflow:

- 1) The Work Card template, i.e., the instrument to develop the content for the e-Magazine. Annex 1 contains the full text about each of the Work Cards.
- 2) The e-Magazine timeline to establish and monitor the periodic production of content and publication.

Work Card template

The Work Card is the document that the researcher must use to develop the content of the article in the e-Magazine. The Work Card template details the instructions to fill it in according to the type of content in case, either a graphical article or a report. Condensed in the following two figures, below we refer to the different elements and recommendations contained in each Work Card. The first image details the elements in the “Work Card report” template model:

Title	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The title must be attractive and attract interest. • It must contain between 40 and 70 characters (10/20 words) • It is very important that the keyword or concept that is developed about the communication appears in the title.
Subtitle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It must contain between 60 and 100 characters (15/40 words) • It is recommended that the subtitle encompass one or two questions, which are answered in the body of the text.
Lead	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief paragraph, between 60 and 70 words, that summarizes the most relevant of the content • It will include the key concepts of the relationship of the analysed resource with communication for projects, results, research actions
Text body	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It contains the details of the subject, organized as far as possible following an inductive logic (from the particular to the general). It can be done as storytelling, starting from a specific case. • As a guide, it will have between 1000 and 1300 words. • It will be written in several short paragraphs. • An idea or concept will be covered per paragraph to facilitate reading.
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most relevant, prominent or shocking information will be closed to keep the interest of the user until the end. • At least a couple of subtitles will be included to divide the text. • Links will be included in the text to other news and information from the blog itself, but also to sources that refer to or external, verified information that serves to complete the content of the post. • The information will be complemented with some multimedia content: an image, an infographic, a video, a table, etc.
Final	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is the last paragraph of the post, so it closes the content. • It must be forceful and include some data or final question that serves as a conclusion and responds to what was raised or expressed in the first paragraphs of the article. • Include methodology when appropriate.
Raw data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please attach the file in .xls or .csv
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When references are used in the text, a list of them will be included following the APA 7th edition model. Whenever possible, the link to the DOI (without references that have it) or to the URL where it is available will be included.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It describes the profile who the text is destined for.

Figure 23. Elements in the template model “Work Card report”

This other image details the different elements in the “Work Card *Graphical article*” template model:

Title	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The title must be a question that will be answered with the data included in the Graphical article • It must contain between 40 and 70 characters (10/20 words) • It is very important that the keyword or concept that is developed about the communication appears in the title.
Excerpt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It must contain between 60 and 100 characters (15/40 words) • It is suggested not to include the answer to the question in order to invite users to read the Graphical article
Highlight 1	Main point that can be highlighted with the data
Highlight 2	Secondary point that can be highlighted with the data
Paragraph 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief paragraph, between 60 and 70 words, that summarizes the most relevant of the content • It will include the key concepts of the relationship of the analysed resource with communication for projects, results, research actions
Paragraph 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As a guide, it contains an explanation about how to interpret/use the data. • It will have between 60 and 70 words. • Include methodology when appropriate
Graphic Screenshot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include a/the screenshot/s of the graphics
Graphic Legend	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include the legend that is necessary to interpret the graphic
Data sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If it is necessary
Graphic data (mandatory)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please attach the file in .xls or .csv that is necessary to create an interactive graphic
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It describes the profile who the text is destined for.

Figure 24. Elements in the template model “Work Card *Graphical article*”

The audience-related items have only recently been included in both templates of the Work Card. The type of the audience, defined previously in Deliverable 5.1, describes the profile that the text is designated for. It should be proposed by the researcher and he/she should choose one priority target and then one or more secondary audience targets between the following:

- [U1] Policymakers and policy influencers.
- [U2] Academics
- [U3] Practitioners.
- [U4] Heads of organizations.
- [U5] Heads and technical managers of civil society organizations and NGO's
- [U6] Heads and technical managers of Industrial organizations
- [U7] Heads and technical managers of training agencies

Planning the e-Magazine

To guarantee the continuity of the e-Magazine publication, a WP and PM-based calendar of contributions has been devised. The following image shows a first tentative version of the plan/timeline, whose realization will depend on the content/results available from the different WPs as the project advances.

DISTRIBUTION BY WP - e-Magazine CS TRACK (Proposal)																									
	2021												2022												
M/WP	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total
WP1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1	1		12
WP2		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1	12
WP3	2		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1				12
WP4			1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1		1	1	12
																									48

Figure 25. Distribution of articles by Work Package

Layout Template

To facilitate the process of publishing the articles, a template has been created with the basic structure to comply with, according to the type of content. This will warrant a homogeneous formal presentation, thus optimizing the production, editing and revision processes.

Figure 26. Layout template of an article

4. Scheduling

4.1. E-Magazine scheduling

According to the Deliverable D5.1, the e-Magazine will feature, overall, 48 articles, which will be published monthly at the rate of 2 articles per month. The launch of the first publication took place at the end of December 2020.

A schedule was created to keep a detailed record of the processes. It contains the following elements: the issue number (IS), the article per month (Ar), the steps of the process (St), the responsible person(s) in each phase (In charge), the type of the content (Graph. Art./Report), the provisional title, the name and his/her email of author, the WP numbers, the status in which each phase is, the deadline and finally the period elapsed. The following image illustrates the above:

POST SCHEDULING - e-Magazine CS TRACK													
IS	Ar	St	Process	Incharge	Graph. art./Report	Provisional Title	Author	Email	WP	Status	Deadline	Cr	
1	1	1	C sends WC to URJC	Author						Pending assignment	12/11/2020	-9	
		2	URJC adapts the content, creates the media, publishes a dr	URJC							Finalized	19/11/2020	-2
		3	C validates the draft	Author							Finalized	10/12/2020	-21
		4	URJC integrates the article in the next issue and send it to t	URJC							Finalized	17/12/2020	-14
	2	1	C sends WC to URJC	Author	Report	Evolution of academic publi	David Roldán (URJC)	david.roldan@urjc.es	WP3	Finalized	12/11/2020	-9	
		2	URJC adapts the content, creates the media, publishes a dr	URJC							Finalized	19/11/2020	-2
		3	C validates the draft	Author							Finalized	10/12/2020	-21
		4	URJC integrates the article in the next issue and send it to t	URJC							Finalized	17/12/2020	-14
				Validation of the e-Magazine issue	Editorial Committee						Finalized	24/12/2020	-7
				URJC publishes the e-Magazine issue	URJC						Finalized	31/12/2020	
2	1	1	C sends WC to URJC	Author						Pending assignment	13/12/2020	-9	
		2	URJC adapts the content, creates the media, publishes a dr	URJC							Finalized	20/12/2020	-2
		3	C validates the draft	Author							Finalized	10/1/2021	-21
		4	URJC integrates the article in the next issue and send it to t	URJC							Finalized	17/1/2021	-14
	2	1	C sends WC to URJC	Author							Pending assignment	13/12/2020	-9
		2	URJC adapts the content, creates the media, publishes a dr	URJC							Finalized	20/12/2020	-2
		3	C validates the draft	Author							Finalized	10/1/2021	-21
		4	URJC integrates the article in the next issue and send it to t	URJC							Finalized	17/1/2021	-14
				Validation of the e-Magazine issue	Editorial Committee						Finalized	24/1/2021	-7
				URJC publishes the e-Magazine issue	URJC						Finalized	31/1/2021	

Figure 27. Post scheduling example

4.2. First Publication

- The first publication in the e-Magazine is a report and it has been published at the end of December 2020.
- Its title is: *Evolution of academic publications in citizen science*.
- David Roldán is the researcher who has written it and he is an internal researcher from WP3.
- In this type of content (report) the commentary system is operational (see sections 2.2 and 2.3, above), as shown in the image below.

In the following images the resulting first article can be seen:

Reading Time: 5 minutes

Citizen science is an area in which interest has increased over the years. People who are not professional scientists get involved in citizen science projects with the intention of solving a question that they find to be of interest. Traditionally, scientific discoveries are accompanied by academic publications that demonstrate the results obtained. However, the non-academic nature of citizen science means that such academic publications are not an intrinsic aspect of citizen science projects. In this post, we show how citizen science publication has evolved over the last 30 years.

Evolution of academic publications

Citizen science is the practice of using a large number of volunteers, rather than professional researchers, to collect data for scientific research. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavours that generate new knowledge or understanding. However, managing a large number of scientists is not a trivial task and in many instances the data provided has limitations and controls for bias need to be introduced. It is well known that the quality of data significantly affects publications in the academic field. Therefore, in this post we show how publications related to citizen science have evolved by using Scopus, an expertly curated abstract and citation database. We are working with a total of 19,182 publications dating from 1990 to 2019. Although citizen science was defined in the mid/1990s by Rick Bonney in the United States (Bonney, 1996) and Alan Irwin in the United Kingdom (Irwin, 1995) it was not until 2005 that the number of academic publications in this area began to grow.

Types of academic publications in citizen science

Since 2005, publications have continued to grow exponentially, peaking in 2019 with a total of 1,995 publications. Academic production is increasing and we wanted to find out the kind of publications that are the most common in this area.

What we discovered is that the greatest effort is put into the creation of journal articles, followed by conference papers. The reader may have noted that in this case only the information about 16,529 publications (of the total 19,182) is shown. This is because 2,653 publications could not be classified, so they have been removed from this visualisation. This is to be expected as research projects in general try to publish in journals with an impact factor. In addition, many citizen science projects seek to make their publications open so that they reach as many people as possible. In this sense, the costs of publication in journals with a high impact factor can be beyond the budget available in certain citizen science projects (Gardemaler et al., 2016).

Type of academic publications

Articles Book Chapter Conference Paper Conference Review Data Paper Erratum Letter Note Review Science Short Survey

A Flounish chart

Just as publications have been growing over the last decade, so has the number of open access publications. The trend in citizen science follows what is happening in academic publication generally. As stated by Europe in its "Trends for open access to publications" report, in 2018, 36.2% of publications were made open access. Regarding citizen science publications, 39.1% of publications were open access in 2019.

Open access publications

Figure 28. Screenshot of the first post 1

Areas of citizen science interest in academic publications

Academic interest is also growing in the citizen science area. As shown in the following chart, the number of citations skyrocketed in 2007, two years after the number of citizen science publications increased substantially. The reason behind this is that a publication usually starts being cited 1-2 years following publication. This is the main reason why after 2007, the number of citations started going down. We need to wait until the end of 2020 to measure the extent to which 2018 publications are being cited. This figure shows that **there is a great deal of interest in citizen science in the academic environment**, however more profound analysis needs to be done to reach more meaningful conclusions.

Conclusion

In this post we have described how academic publications in the area of citizen science have grown in the last 30 years. This is based on a small sample taken from Scopus, so further databases need to be consulted in order to better understand how the results of citizen science projects are published as well as how such publications are contributing to a broader understanding of science in general. Our investigation clearly shows how interest in citizen science continues to grow, however more information needs to be gathered on how specific related research areas are developing. In CS Track project we hope to be able to contribute to this knowledge by investigating the areas of research in which citizen science initiatives are most often focused as well as the areas which give rise to the most academic publications.

REFERENCES

Audience: [Academics](#) | [Heads of organizations](#) | [Practitioners](#)

Categories: [Reports](#)

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Figure 29. Screenshot of the first post 2

5. Editorial Guidelines

5.1. Editorial standards and Style guide

To ensure the best text editing work for our e-Magazine, the Editorial Guidelines of the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) will be used; there are available in <https://www.bbc.com/editorialguidelines>

Likewise, the BBC style guide <https://www.bbc.co.uk/newsstyleguide> will be followed; this guide details many of the rules of spelling, punctuation and grammar, as well as issues of accuracy, fairness and impartiality.

5.2. Gender considerations

In the analysis of users of the platform done in the Deliverable 5.1, the gender perspective was estimated.

In the writing and editing of the articles, the ethical and gender requirements established in the CS-Track project and, specifically, the provisions of Deliverable 8.1 will be followed. As well, we will follow the recommendations of the European [Portal GenPORT](#) (European Union, 2014) which provides information about gender and science to publish material, reports or articles.

Further, the stereotypes of sex and gender will be considered when we have to generate ideas to rethink language (word choice, metaphors, analogies, and naming practices) and visual representations (images, tables, and graphs) as it is suggested in [Gendered Innovations How Gender Analysis Contributes to Research, European Commission](#) (Schiebinger, 2013) and in [Gender-responsive communications toolkit](#) (IOM, 2020)

5.3. Ethical considerations

In the requirements' specification for the community platform detailed in Deliverable 5.1 it was established that the data collected from registered and non-registered users of the CS TRACK project will fall within the scope of the standard operation of research projects funded under H2020.

Also, that access to the data will comply with the data security and ethical aspects described in sections 4 and 5 of Deliverable D7.1 - Data Management Plan.

In the implementation of e-Magazine we have followed the principles of information law and consent. According to the General Data Protection Regulation (RGPD). (UE 2016/679) all personal data are stored securely.

The mitigation measures undertaken include providing visibility to privacy and cookies policy within the website of the CS Track project <https://cstrack.eu/privacy-cookies-policy/>

The data stored will be the following: username, the name and surname, and email. Other information required, if at all, will be provided (or not) on a voluntary basis. In the case of users without registration, personal details are not registered. In these cases, only the information related to cookies detailed in Deliverable 5.1 is stored.

6. References

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7. Annexes

7.1. Annex 1: Work Card e-Magazine

The original idea of Community Platform

Figure 30. original idea of Community Platform

The final version of the newsletter.

Here it comes!! Our newsletter... Citizen Science doesn't give up! As usual, we send you the eMagazine articles, that usually present reports, technical notes and articles about CSTrack project. In addition, we include the news & events section, which a selection of curated information about Citizen Science. Lastly, you will find an overview about communication actions from CS Track project.

Latest eMagazine articles

[\(Draft\) Evolution of academic publications in citizen science](#)

Academic publications are the result of research experiments. Due to the non-academic nature of citizen science, research is not usually carried out with the aim of publishing academic articles. Are there scientific publications related to citizen science?

[\(Draft\) Social network analysis for the chimp & see citizen science project](#)

Zooniverse platform is one of the larger citizen science web portals. One of the projects on the Zooniverse platform is Chimp & See. Would you like to find out about this project? Let us tell you how awesome it is!

CS Track news & events

[Meet CS Track at the SDG Citizen Science conference Berlin on 14-15 October](#)

[New release of EU-Citizen.Science Platform offers lots of additional features](#)

[Plans for creating a Community Platform for CS Track take shape](#)

[JYU brings CS Track to Bioeconomy workshop in Finland](#)

CStrack overview

Despite the current pandemic, CS Track partners have continued to be busy working on the project these past 3 months. Much of this work was presented and discussed at the project partners' meeting, held as a marathon online event spread over 3 days at the start of May.

Figure 31. Final version of the newsletter

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